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Smoothed Seismicity Model Underlying ESHM20

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Abstract: The European Seismic Hazard Model 2020 (ESHM20, Danciu et al 2021,2024) is based on the ESHM13 model but with newly generated local and regional seismogenic sources. One of the main components of the ESHM20 is a smoothed seismicity model (SSM). It is based on the premise that previous earthquakes' spatial location and magnitude distribution predict future earthquakes' likely location and size. This model uses smoothing kernels to estimate the probable location of future seismicity by smoothing the location of past declustered earthquakes. Critical choices in forecasting using an SSM include (1) the adaptiveness of the kernel's bandwidth, (2) the smoothing parameters, (3) the declustering procedure, and (4) the declustering parameters. We use a one-fold cross-validation approach to find the optimal smoothing parameters using only the training set. We use this approach to identify a reference smoothed seismicity model, which relies on declustered catalogues obtained from window-based declustering. We subject this SSM to numerous retrospective tests to demonstrate its consistency with the past seismicity. Finally, we perform a pseudo-prospective experiment to identify the best combination of choices that could be made to obtain the most suitable SSM for use with the seismogenic source model of ESHM20.

Keywords: smoothed seismicity model, declustering, forecasting, seismic hazard, European seismic hazard model, ESHM20

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1. Introduction

The seismogenic source model of ESHM20 (Danciu et al 2021, 2024) is built upon the foundation of the ESHM13 (Woessner et al. 2015), enhanced with newly developed local and regional seismogenic sources. One of the main components of this model is a seismicity rate forecast based on smoothing the location of past earthquakes. This model uses the idea that past earthquakes' spatial and magnitude distribution reveal the probable location and size of future seismicity. Smoothed seismicity models have been widely used in the literature to forecast future earthquakes (Kagan and Jackson, 1994; Woo, 1996; Cao et al., 1996; Jackson and Kagan, 1999; Stock and Smith, 2002a, 2002b; Helmstetter et al., 2006; Helmstetter et al., 2007; Zechar and Jordan, 2010; Werner et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2011; Helmstetter and Werner, 2012; Rhoades et al., 2012; Hiemer et al., 2013, 2014; Hiemer and Kamer, 2016; Nandan et al., 2019).

The wide prevalence of the SSMs in the literature can probably be attributed to the relative ease with which these models can be constructed and their success in forecasting future seismicity. The model based on the smoothed seismicity approach has been found to be the most successful model in the first prospective forecasting experiment conducted by the Regional Earthquake Likelihood Models (RELM) experiment (Zechar et al., 2013; Rhoades et al., 2014). These models have outperformed many seismicity-based models and those that have incorporated strain and mapped fault information.

The training set is used to generate the smoothed seismicity model (SSM) for a specific combination of modelling choices, while the validation set is employed to evaluate and rank the resulting SSMs using a pre-defined metric, specifically, the information gain per earthquake. To identify the optimal SSM for the ESHM20 framework, we systematically explored four key modelling dimensions:

- (1) the type of smoothing kernel (adaptive vs. non-adaptive),
- (2) the parameters controlling the shape and scale of the kernel,
- (3) the declustering algorithm used to filter dependent events, and
- (4) the internal parameters of each declustering method.

A total of 442 candidate SSMs were generated by combining these choices. Each model was trained on the earthquake catalogue up to the end of 2006 and evaluated on an independent validation set consisting of seismicity recorded between 2007 and 2015. This pseudo-prospective testing framework mimics forward-looking forecasting conditions, providing an unbiased comparison of model performance across the Euro-Mediterranean region.

For all models, the smoothing parameters were optimized using a leave-one-out cross-validation approach, and model outputs were evaluated on a common $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid using the log-likelihood of observed event locations.

As part of the evaluation process, a reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM) was constructed using the Grünthal window-based declustering algorithm, previously adopted as the standard approach in ESHM13 (Woessner et al., 2015). This model, in combination with an adaptive power-law smoothing kernel, was subjected to a series of retrospective consistency tests to assess its ability to reproduce observed earthquake rates across multiple magnitude ranges and tectonic zones. The results demonstrated that the reference SSM provides a statistically consistent and spatially meaningful forecast of long-term seismicity patterns across the Euro-Mediterranean region.

The outcomes of both the retrospective validation and the pseudo-prospective performance evaluation informed the selection of the final reference model used in ESHM20. Although several alternative SSMs, particularly those based on Gardner–Knopoff or Uhrhammer window-based declustering, showed marginally higher forecast skill in terms of information gain, the reference model was ultimately chosen due to its robustness, alignment with prior modelling efforts, and suitability for integration within the large-scale hazard computation workflow. The structure of this report is as follows:

Section 2 introduces the unified earthquake catalogue and its properties. Section 3 describes additional modelling inputs for SSMs, including magnitude completeness and Gutenberg–Richter parameters. Section 4 documents the construction of the reference SSM, including:

- 4.1: incorporation of space-time varying completeness,
- 4.2: smoothing kernel optimization using leave-one-out cross-validation,
- 4.3: comparison between adaptive and non-adaptive kernels, and
- 4.4: retrospective consistency testing.

Section 5 presents the pseudo-prospective experiments used to evaluate 442 SSM variants. Section 6 summarizes the key conclusions and implications for seismic hazard modelling in ESHM20; and Section 7 (Appendix) provides supplementary spatial maps of normalized cumulative seismicity rates at various magnitude thresholds for the reference SSM.

Important to note, that the reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM) presented in this manuscript is developed exclusively for shallow crustal seismicity, consistent with the modelling focus of the main ESHM20 framework. A similar methodology, including adaptive kernel smoothing and declustering-based rate estimation, was independently applied for other seismogenic domains. Specifically, smoothed seismicity models were also developed for deep intermediate-depth seismicity in the Vrancea region (Romania) and for in-slab subduction seismicity, using the corresponding earthquake catalogues and region-specific completeness as well as their tectonic regionalization.

Table 1: Summary statistics of the ESHM20 and the ESHM13 unified earthquake catalogues

	(1) Historical: SERA v1.0	(2) Instrumental: EMEC v20190218	(1)+(2): Unified ESHM20	Compare Unified ESHM13
Time span	1000/1900	1900/31-12-2014	1000/31-12-2014	1000/31-12-2006
Magnitude span	1.9/8.5	3.49/8.3	1.7/8.5	1.7/8.5
Longitude span	-23.5°/32.413°	-37.0°/51.9°	-37.0°/51.9°	-31.65°/45.0°
Latitude span	35.0°/69.43°	26.9°/73.0°	26.9°/73.0°	33.2°/73.32°
# Total Number	5716	55411	61127	30012
# magnitude \geq 4.5	2340	20388	22728	13284
# magnitude \geq 5.0	1552	6013	7565	5585
# magnitude \geq 5.5	885	1920	2805	2066
# NaN depth	4971	9451	14422	10616
# NaN magnitudes	282	0	282	303
# depth < 40km	5355	49436	54791	25666

2. Input Datasets

In this study, we use the unified earthquake catalogue curated for the Euro-Mediterranean region, developed as the primary seismicity input for the ESHM20 model. This cross-border harmonized catalogue includes both historical and instrumental seismicity, spanning approximately 1,000 years and ending in December 2014.

The unified catalogue (Danciu et al., 2021b) comprises 56,437 earthquakes across the broader European region (Figure 1) and represents a significant update compared to the dataset used in ESHM13 (Stucchi et al., 2013). The historical component is based on EPICA v1.1 (Rovida et al., 2022; Rovida and Antonucci, 2021), covering the period 1000–1899 CE and built upon the European Archive of Historical Earthquake Data (AHEAD) (Locati et al., 2014; Rovida and Locati, 2015). It

includes 5,703 events, many of which were re-evaluated using harmonized macroseismic methodologies to ensure consistency across national borders.

The instrumental portion of the catalogue, spanning 1900–2014, is based on the updated European-Mediterranean Earthquake Catalogue (EMEC) (Lammers et al., 2023). This catalogue extends the version previously used in ESHM13 (Grünthal and Wahlström, 2012; Grünthal et al., 2013) and contains over 55,700 earthquakes with moment magnitude $M_w > 3.5$. EMEC integrates data from various regional and national sources and applies region-specific source prioritization and magnitude conversion procedures to ensure a consistent and harmonized magnitude scale.

Compared to ESHM13, the ESHM20 earthquake catalogue extends the temporal coverage by an additional eight years and expands the spatial domain across the Euro-Mediterranean region. As a result, it includes a significantly greater number of events. Even when limited to the common period 1900–2007, the ESHM20 catalogue contains more earthquakes across most magnitude thresholds (Figure 2). Summary statistics for both catalogues are presented in Table 1.

However, the increase in event counts is not spatially uniform. The difference in the number of events (Δ) between ESHM20 and ESHM13 varies considerably across regions and magnitude bins. For instance, in Italy, ESHM20 includes substantially more earthquakes at lower magnitudes (e.g., $M \geq 3.5$), whereas at $M \geq 4.5$, the ESHM13 catalogue records a greater number of events. This variability highlights the differences in regional catalogue updates, completeness, and source inclusion criteria between the two models.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution and magnitude of all earthquakes reported in the ESHM20 earthquake catalogue. The crustal faults are illustrated with grey lines.

Figure 2: Spatial variation of difference in the number of events between the ESHM20 and ESHM13 catalogue for different magnitude thresholds. Warmer and cooler colours indicate regions where ESHM20 and ESHM13 catalogue features more events within the 1900–2007 time-period.

3. Additional inputs for the SSMs

Additionally, the smoothed seismicity model utilizes the space-time varying completeness. This space-time varying completeness is encoded into time-varying completeness curves for pre-defined completeness source zones (CSZs). It is thus assumed that a given CSZ has experienced the same incompleteness function during its entire history.

The completeness time series for a given CSZ is determined using an improved version of the widely used temporal course of earthquake frequency (TCEF) method [Stepp, 1972; Nasir et al., 2013].

This method has been improved in the ESHM20 by incorporating standard statistical tests and the non-parametric maximum curvature method. This improved method, which allows for automatic detection of completeness time steps, is applied to the ESHM20 earthquake unified catalogue enclosed within the 48 completeness superzones redefined to depict the seismicity patterns and the development of the seismic networks in the region (Danciu et al 2021). Figure 3 shows an example completeness time series obtained by applying the improved method to the CSZ with id SZ02.

Figure 3: a) Comparison of the magnitude of completeness time steps obtained using the improved TCEF method (solid blue line) and expert-driven magnitude of completeness time steps (dashed blue line) for CSZ_CH; Orange and black circles indicate the time and magnitude of the declustered and clustered earthquake events; Only declustered data is used to obtain the completeness time steps; b) Consistency between the empirical annualized frequency magnitude distribution obtained using the expert-driven magnitude of completeness (orange circles) and best fit theoretical GR distribution; Maximum likelihood estimate of the a and b-value and their 95% confidence interval are indicated at the top of the panel; c) Same as panel (b) but for the completeness time steps obtained using the improved TCEF method; d) area of completeness super zone highlighted in blue; location of the declustered and clustered seismicity.

A very important input for the smoothed seismicity model is the TECTO zonation layer, which organizes the model region into polygons with homogeneous geological, geophysical, and seismological characteristics (Danciu et al 2021).

As shown in Figure 4, each TECTO polygon encompasses multiple seismogenic sources and serves as the spatial unit for estimating Gutenberg-Richter activity parameters. The estimation of a-b GR params of the smoothed seismicity model follows the assumption that regional seismicity behaves as a stationary Poisson process, characterized by a constant mean rate of occurrence. These parameters are derived from the declustered unified earthquake catalogue and as mentioned above accounts for magnitude–time completeness.

The estimates of the Gutenberg–Richter (GR) parameters and the corresponding values of the maximum magnitude M_{max} are shown in Figure 4. The value of M_{max} is derived from a double-truncated magnitude-frequency distribution and corresponds to the magnitude at which the annual recurrence rate falls below 10^{-6} . As such, the estimate of M_{max} is entirely data-driven, based on observed seismicity as well as the forecasted seismicity, and provides an internally consistent upper bound for each TECTO zone. This contrasts with the M_{max} values used in the area source models, which are typically conservative expert-judgment based and historical observations (see Danciu et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Estimates of the three input parameters used for deriving smoothed seismicity models. Top-left, top-right and bottom panels show the estimate of a -value, b -value and M_{max} estimate for each of the TECTO polygons, whose boundaries are delineated using white lines in each of the panel.

4. Reference Smoothed Seismicity Model (SSM)

This section describes the development of the reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM) used in ESHM20. The purpose of the SSM is to provide a continuous, data-driven representation of seismicity rates across Europe by smoothing the spatial distribution of past earthquakes. Developed from the declustered unified earthquake catalogue, the model serves as a critical component of the overall source model framework, particularly in regions where mapped faults are sparse or absent.

The SSM is used as an alternative to traditional area source models in regions lacking well-defined fault systems, and as a background seismicity model to account for off-fault activity and the rates of

lower-magnitude events occurring on faults (see Danciu et al., 2021, 2024). By capturing the spatial patterns of seismicity clustering, the model also reflects how seismicity tends to concentrate and potentially migrate within broader tectonic domains, as defined by the TECTO zonation layer.

Only independent and complete earthquakes are kept for smoothing after the input catalogue is filtered for space-time completeness using an improved TCEF approach and dependent events are removed using window-based declustering. The remaining independent, complete events are then smoothed using a power-law kernel, with parameters optimized through a leave-one-out cross-validation strategy.

Both adaptive and non-adaptive smoothing approaches were evaluated. The adaptive method was preferred, as it dynamically adjusts the bandwidth of the smoothing kernel based on local seismicity density, providing finer resolution in seismically active regions and broader smoothing where data are sparse.

To calibrate the parameters of the power-law kernel, we applied a leave-one-out cross-validation procedure (LOOCV). In this approach, each earthquake in the training catalogue is temporarily excluded, and the model is built using the remaining data. The likelihood of the omitted event is then evaluated under the resulting model. This process is repeated for all events, and the overall performance is measured by aggregating the likelihood scores. LOOCV provides a robust way to optimize model parameters without requiring a separate validation dataset, ensuring that the smoothing captures the underlying spatial patterns without overfitting to individual events.

Finally, the resulting seismicity rates are tested against observed earthquake counts in different tectonic regions and magnitude intervals. These retrospective consistency checks confirm the statistical validity and practical applicability of the reference model.

4.1 Accounting for space-time varying completeness in SSM

The first step in estimating the SSM is finding the pivot points, which mark the locations where the smoothing kernels are placed. The pivot points are obtained by first applying the declustering filter to all the earthquakes in a CSZ. In other words, all earthquakes within a given CSZ that belong to the list of declustered earthquakes within that CSZ are selected as pivot points. This list of pivot points is further trimmed by selecting only those earthquakes that can be labelled as complete based on the completeness time series within that CSZ.

As the different regions have different completeness histories, we cannot simply smooth the pivot points to obtain SSM. Otherwise, this would lead to exaggeration of rates in the regions which have a long history of recordings or lower magnitude of completeness (M_c) values. To bring all the regions on the same footing, each pivot point should be weighted so that their total sum within a TECTO zone reflects the yearly seismicity rate at any reference magnitude level.

The choice of this reference magnitude is unimportant, and we set it to 4.5. We use the a-b values estimated in each TECTO polygons to estimate the yearly rate in each TECTO polygon. Each pivot point in the polygon is then assigned a weight in the polygon, which is given by the following formula:

$$w_{i,k} = \frac{10^{-b_k * M_t + a_k}}{N_k} \quad (1)$$

N_k is the total number of pivot points within a k^{th} polygon.

4.2 Optimizing smoothing parameters using leave-one-out cross-validation

The next step in defining the SSM is to obtain the smoothed seismicity rate at any location using weighted pivot points and a smoothing kernel. We select an isotropic power-law kernel for this purpose. This kernel can feature adaptive bandwidth.

We first described the case for non-adaptive bandwidth and then extended it for the case of adaptive bandwidth. Using this smoothing kernel, the yearly seismicity rate above M_t at any location is described as:

$$\mu(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \pi^{-1} Q D^Q ((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2 + D)^{-1-Q} \quad (2)$$

Here, i is the index of pivot points in the list L , which is comprised of all the pivot points from all the TECTO polygons. The corresponding weight of the pivot point is w_i , is defined in Equation 1. Note that we have dropped the index k , used in Equation 1 to represent the identity of the TECTO polygon for the sake of simplicity of representation. $\pi^{-1} Q D^Q ((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2 + D)^{-1-Q}$ is the power-law smoothing kernel with two parameters: exponent, Q and regularizer D . $\pi^{-1} Q D^Q$ ensures that the kernel integrates to 1 for x, y in $[-\infty, \infty]$.

The parameters D and Q are unknown *a priori* and must be optimized. To optimize the parameters, we use the following leave-one-out cross-validation scheme.

We first define the spatial probability density function of the background earthquakes at the j^{th} pivot point with as:

$$\mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j) = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j}^N w_i \pi^{-1} Q D^Q ((x_j - x_i)^2 + (y_j - y_i)^2 + D)^{-1-Q}}{\sum_{i \neq j}^N w_i} \quad (3)$$

Using $\mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j)$ and w_j , we can define the complete data log-likelihood for the spatial distribution of the pivot points (x_j, y_j) with corresponding weight w_j as:

$$LL_{bkg} = \sum_{j=1}^N w_j \times \ln \mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j) \quad (4)$$

LL_{bkg} can be optimized with respect to the parameters D and Q . To obtain $\mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j)$, the summation in the right-hand side of the Equation is done for $i \neq j$, which amounts to a leave-one-out cross-validation strategy.

To obtain SSM based on the power-law kernel with adaptive bandwidth, we follow the strategy prescribed in Silverman [1998].

1. We first find a pilot estimate, $\mu_{pilot}(x, y)$, of SSM. In fact, we use the $\mu(x, y)$ defined in Equation 2 with the optimized parameters D and Q as our pilot estimates.
2. Next, we define local bandwidth factors at the location of i^{th} pivot point as :

$$\lambda_i = \left(\frac{\mu(x_i, y_i)}{g} \right)^{-\alpha} \quad (5)$$

Where g is the geometric mean of $\mu(x_i, y_i)$ and α is the sensitivity parameter with values between 0 and 1. The value of α controls how sensitive the bandwidth is to the local density. In this study, we set $\alpha = 0.5$ based on the recommendations in ref.

3. The SSM model based on the adaptive kernel is then defined as:

$$\mu(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \pi^{-1} Q D_i^{Q_{adapt}} ((x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2 + D_i)^{-1-Q_{adapt}} \quad (6)$$

where, $D_i = D_{adapt} \times \lambda_i^2$.

We again have two parameters to optimize D_{adapt} and Q_{adapt} . These can be optimized in the same leave-one-out cross-validation approach defined earlier.

4.3 Adaptive vs Non-Adaptive Kernels

Figure 5 shows the estimate of $\mu(x, y)$ (≥ 4.5) on a regular grid of resolution ($0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$). Panel (a) corresponds to the non-adaptive power-law kernel, while panel (b) corresponds to the adaptive power-law kernel. The estimates of the parameters $D, Q, D_{adapt}, Q_{adapt}$ are approximately 275, 0.74, 2000, 1.96, respectively. The adaptive kernel adjusts the "bandwidth" of the smoothing kernel depending on the local density of seismicity. Areas with high seismic density have smaller bandwidth and vice-versa. As a result, the adaptive $\mu(x, y)$ has more details in seismically active regions and smoother variations in low activity regions. On the contrary, the $\mu(x, y)$ based on the non-adaptive kernel has a similar level of detail in all regions irrespective of the seismic density.

The non-adaptiveness of the bandwidth gives it a less desirable patchier appearance. In terms of LL_{bkg} defined in Equation 4, we find that the non-adaptive and adaptive SSMs obtain a score of -1363.8 and -1356.2, respectively, providing another justification for the adaptive SSM.

Figure 5: Optimal SSM using a) non-adaptive power-law kernel b) adaptive power-law kernel.

To illustrate the spatial pattern of the reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM) across different magnitude thresholds, Figure 6 presents spatial maps of the background seismicity rate density $\mu(x, y)$ derived using the adaptive power-law kernel. Each panel displays the forecasted annualized seismicity rates (in \log_{10} units of events/ km^2/year) for increasing magnitude thresholds: $M \geq 4.5, 5.1, 5.7, 6.3, 6.9,$ and 7.5 .

As expected, the spatial extent and intensity of seismicity forecasts decrease with increasing magnitude threshold, reflecting the exponential decay of event frequency consistent with the Gutenberg–Richter distribution. Regions of persistent high background rates, such as the Hellenic Arc, eastern Türkiye, and parts of southern Italy, remain visible even at higher magnitude thresholds, although their spatial footprint diminishes substantially.

The values displayed above each panel indicate the total expected number of events per year for the entire mapped area. These values decrease from approximately 88 events/year for $M \geq 4.5$ to less than 0.1 events/year for $M \geq 7.5$, illustrating the sparsity of large-magnitude background events.

It should be noted that the region of Iceland is not included in these preliminary maps, as the earthquake catalogue data for this area were not available at the time of map generation. However, the final reference SSM results, including Iceland and updated catalogue coverage, are provided in the Appendix.

Finally, in the vicinity of mapped faults, the smoothed seismicity model only contributes to the off-fault seismicity, with earthquake occurrence rates for larger magnitudes being controlled by the fault-based source models (see Section 3.3). These maps therefore represent only the background (non-associated) component of seismicity in faulted regions.

It is important to note that in the vicinity of known faults, the background SSM only contributes to off-fault seismicity. In these regions, the total earthquake occurrence rates for large magnitudes are controlled by the fault-based seismogenic sources (see Section 3.3, Danciu et al 2021). Therefore, the smoothed background model effectively captures only the diffuse, non-associated seismicity at higher magnitude thresholds in these zones.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of the annualized smoothed seismicity rate $\mu(x,y)$ computed using the adaptive power-law kernel for six magnitude thresholds: (a) $M \geq 4.5$, (b) $M \geq 5.1$, (c) $M \geq 5.7$, (d) $M \geq 6.3$, (e) $M \geq 6.9$, and (f) $M \geq 7.5$. The total annual rate (events/year) for each magnitude threshold is shown above each panel. The maps display $\log_{10}[\text{Rate of } M \geq M_i \text{ (events/km}^2\text{/year)}]$. The highest intensities are concentrated in the Hellenic region, western Anatolia, and southern Italy, with the extent and intensity decreasing with increasing magnitude threshold, as expected from the Gutenberg–Richter scaling. The model accounts only for off-fault background rates in fault-buffer regions.

4.4 Retrospective consistency tests

To assess the robustness of the reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM), we conducted a series of retrospective consistency tests. These tests examine how well the model reproduces observed earthquake rates over long-term completeness-adjusted windows, stratified by tectonic polygon and magnitude interval. Specifically, we focus here on the magnitude interval 5.0–5.6 and perform the analysis at the TECTO polygon level.

The consistency evaluation follows a Poisson-based framework that compares the forecasted number of events in each TECTO polygon to the observed earthquake counts, considering catalogue completeness. The key steps of the procedure are as follows:

1. **Determination of Completeness Duration:** For each TECTO polygon k , the completeness duration T_k is established as the number of years during which the earthquake catalogue is deemed complete for the magnitude threshold of $M_w = 5.0$. This threshold corresponds to the lower bound of the magnitude bin considered in the analysis. Completeness windows were derived from space–time varying completeness intervals established as part of the ESHM20 workflow (Danciu et al 2021).
2. **Observed Earthquake Counts:** Earthquakes in the magnitude range 5.0–5.6 that occurred in the time window $[2015 - T_k, 2015]$ are extracted from the declustered and completeness-filtered unified earthquake catalogue. The resulting count, $N_{k,obs}$, serves as the empirical benchmark for comparison.
3. **Forecasted Earthquake Rates:** For each TECTO polygon k , the expected number of events is calculated by integrating the smoothed seismicity rate $\mu(x,y)$ over the polygon area S_k and multiplying by the completeness duration: $N_{k,forecast} = \int_{S_k} \mu(x,y) dx dy \times T_k$, where S_k spatial region of the TECTO polygon k .
4. **Consistency Assessment:** The forecast is deemed consistent if $N_{k,obs}$ falls within the 95% CI of a Poisson distribution with a mean rate $N_{k,forecast}$. The 95% CI of the Poisson distribution are shown as error bars in the panel a, whereas the forecasted numbers $N_{k,forecast}$ are shown as bars. This gives the model’s long-term prediction for the expected number of independent events in the specified magnitude range and spatial domain.

The results of this test are summarized in Figure 7, which presents multiple visualization panels to support interpretation:

- **Panel (a): Forecasted vs. Observed Counts with Confidence Intervals** Each bar represents the forecasted number of events $N_{k,forecast}$ for a specific TECTO polygon. Green bars indicate consistency between the model and observations; red bars denote polygons where the observed count falls outside the 95% Poisson CI, suggesting potential under- or overestimation. Blue diamond markers represent the observed number of earthquakes, and the completeness duration T_k is shown above each bar.
- **Panel (b): Difference in Annualized Rates:** the difference between forecasted and observed annual rates is computed and visualized for each polygon. This provides a direct measure of model bias and helps identify regions where discrepancies are systematic.
- **Panel (c): Spatial Consistency Map:** this map illustrates spatial patterns in consistency. TECTO polygons are shaded green where forecasts and observations agree and red where inconsistencies are observed. This spatial perspective highlights regional clusters of model underperformance or strength.
- **Panel (d): Scatter Plot of Forecasted vs. Observed Counts:** Forecasted and observed event counts are plotted for all TECTO polygons. Points near the red 1:1 line indicate close agreement between model predictions and actual data. Outliers highlight zones where the model may require further calibration.

The retrospective analysis shows that the reference SSM provides a statistically sound and geographically consistent representation of seismicity rates across the Euro-Mediterranean region. In nearly all TECTO polygons, the observed event counts fall within the 95% Poisson CI of the model predictions. The few discrepancies observed are generally within ± 2 events, an expected fluctuation for a process governed by Poissonian statistics.

Figure 7: Consistency between the observed and forecasted rates for the magnitude interval 5.6-6 for different TECTO Zones. (a) Bar plots showing the consistency of the rates forecasted by the reference SSM in the magnitude range [5-5.6]. If the forecast is consistent, the bars are shown in green colour whereas bars corresponding to inconsistent forecasts are shown in red; Completeness duration (T_k) in number of years is written on top of each bar; the Observed number of earthquakes are shown as blue diamond markers; Forecasted numbers are shown as bars; 95% CI of the Poisson distribution are shown as error bars. (b) The difference in yearly forecasted and observed rates. (c) Spatial consistency plots for reference SSM in the magnitude range. (d) Forecasted vs observed number of earthquakes in the four magnitude intervals (indicated at the top of the panel) for the reference SSM. $Y=X$ line is shown in red for reference.

5. Pseudo-prospective experiments with different SSMs

To evaluate the sensitivity and robustness of the smoothed seismicity model (SSM) used in ESHM20, we conducted a set of pseudo-prospective experiments. The goal of these experiments was to assess the relative performance of SSMs constructed using different combinations of modeling assumptions and to inform the selection of alternative models for the source model logic tree.

The tested configurations vary across several key modeling dimensions:

- Smoothing kernel type: Power-law with adaptive vs non-adaptive bandwidths
- Parameters of the smoothing kernels, the shape parameter Q and the regularizer D ;
- Declustering algorithms (Window-based vs Reasenberg vs Zaliapin)
- Parameters of the declustering algorithms
 1. Window-based methods: Grünthal, Gardener-Knopoff, Uhrhammer, Coppersmith)
 2. Reasenberg algorithm
 3. Zaliapin: standard parameters

Each SSM was constructed using the methodology described in Sections 4.1–4.2, with the smoothing kernel parameters optimized directly on the training dataset, consisting of all earthquakes up to and including the year 2006. In total, 442 SSMs were generated for this experiment.

Each SSM is evaluated using an out-of-sample catalog ($M \geq M_t = 4.5$) between 2007 and 2015. Spatial forecasts were generated on a uniform grid with a resolution of $\sim 10 \times 10$ km. Unlike conventional Poisson-based likelihood evaluations, we used a spatial probability density function

(PDF) evaluation approach to avoid dependence on specific declustering assumptions in the validation set.

This approach isolates the model’s ability to forecast the location of future seismicity, independent of rate mismatches introduced by different event clustering levels. Information gain of all models is evaluated against the reference SSM model based on Grünthal window-based declustering with adaptive bandwidth (see Section 4).

Figure 8: Information gain per earthquake (IGPE) of different SSMs relative of the reference SSM (Window based, Grünthal windows, adaptive bandwidth); empty and filled markers correspond to SSM with non-Adaptive and adaptive bandwidth, respectively; black stars indicate if the IGPE is significantly larger than 0 (p -value of a pairwise T-test < 0.05)

The log-likelihood (LL) is obtained on the validation set by comparing the spatial pdf of forecasted background earthquakes to the observed earthquakes in the testing period.

$$LL = \sum_j w_j \times \ln \mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j) \quad (7)$$

$\mu_{PDF}(x_j, y_j)$ is the forecasted spatial PDF background earthquake at the location of j^{th} earthquake in the testing catalog.

The Poisson likelihood is not used since there is no preferable declustering method for defining the background earthquakes for the testing period. Choosing one may tip the scales in favour of the chosen declustering algorithm. Furthermore, when all the earthquakes are used, the forecasted and observed rates will mismatch by construction, causing the scales to tip in favor of a less aggressive declustering method.

Using a purely spatial PDF entirely avoids the problem of rates at the cost of just evaluating the methods based on their ability to forecast only the location of future seismicity.

Information gain of model A over model B is defined as:

$$IG_{AB} = LL_A - LL_B \quad (8)$$

Figure 8 summarizes the results of the pseudo-prospective evaluation, presenting the information gain per earthquake (IGPE) for all tested SSM configurations relative to the reference model, which uses Grünthal window-based declustering in combination with an adaptive power-law kernel. Across all experiments, models employing adaptive bandwidths consistently outperformed their non-adaptive counterparts, confirming the importance of local smoothing adjustments in capturing the spatial variability of seismicity.

Among the alternatives, the highest-performing models were based on the Gardner–Knopoff window combined with adaptive smoothing. Additionally, several configurations using the Uhrhammer

declustering method and specific Reasenber parameter combinations also showed statistically significant improvements over the reference model. Statistical significance was evaluated using paired t-tests, with black stars in the figure indicating cases where $p < 0.05$.

While these alternative models demonstrated superior spatial forecasting skill, they were not implemented as standalone seismogenic source models in the final hazard calculations. This was primarily due to computational constraints, which limited the number of SSM variants that could be included in the ESHM20 hazard logic tree.

To ensure that this decision did not compromise model performance, targeted sensitivity analyses were conducted. These focused on off-fault regions, in the central and northern Europe, where smoothed seismicity plays a dominant role and alternative models might have the most impact.

The analyses confirmed that the differences in resulting hazard estimates were generally not significant. Therefore, the adoption of a single, well-performing reference SSM was considered adequate for ESHM20, balancing scientific rigour with computational feasibility.

Furthermore, these results of this testing framework, underscore the critical influence of both the declustering strategy and the use of adaptive smoothing on the quality of spatial seismicity forecasts. This influence is particularly relevant in regions of low seismicity, where smoothed seismicity may represent the only seismogenic source, and therefore requires careful methodological consideration.

6. Conclusion

This study systematically explored the design and evaluation of Smoothed Seismicity Models (SSMs) within the ESHM20 framework. We examined four critical modelling components: the choice of smoothing kernel (adaptive vs. non-adaptive), kernel parameter optimization, declustering algorithm, and the treatment of catalogue completeness.

Using a one-fold cross-validation approach, we identified a reference SSM constructed from the Grünthal window-based declustered catalogue and an adaptive power-law smoothing kernel. This model provided a statistically consistent and spatially coherent representation of background seismicity, as confirmed through extensive retrospective consistency tests across multiple magnitude thresholds and TECTO zones.

To evaluate the robustness and generalizability of the modeling approach, we conducted pseudo-prospective experiments on over 440 alternative SSM configurations. The results showed that SSMs using adaptive bandwidths consistently outperformed fixed-bandwidth counterparts, and that declustering methods such as Gardner–Knopoff, Uhrhammer, and select Reasenber parameterizations led to statistically significant improvements in information gain over the reference model.

Although these alternative SSMs outperformed the reference configuration in forecast skill, their inclusion in the final ESHM20 hazard model was constrained by computational feasibility. Sensitivity analyses showed that differences in hazard outcomes were minor, especially in regions where smoothed seismicity is the dominant contributor (i.e., areas without mapped active faults), supporting the decision to adopt a single reference SSM.

The reference SSM was also evaluated as part of a hybrid seismogenic source model, where it serves two distinct roles:

- In regions without active fault models, the SSM functions as the primary seismic source, capturing the distributed background seismicity.

- In regions with active faults, the SSM complements the fault models by representing off-fault seismicity and low-magnitude activity not attributed to specific fault geometries. A fault-dependent magnitude threshold is used to avoid double counting, ensuring that larger magnitudes are only assigned to the fault-based source models.

To support reproducibility and visualization of the final SSM, Appendix A provides spatial maps of the yearly cumulative earthquake rates from the reference SSM for four magnitude thresholds ($M \geq 4.5$, 5.1, 6.1, and 7.1). These maps highlight the spatial concentration and decay of seismicity across Europe and surrounding regions and illustrate how the smoothed model transitions from dense clustering in active regions to sparse background rates elsewhere.

Finally, the resulting reference SSM was implemented in OpenQuake (Pagani et al 2014) as part of the final seismogenic source system, alongside active fault and area source models, and used in the ESHM20 hazard computations. All input data, computational files, and additional plots supporting this work are openly available in the ESHM20 repository: <https://gitlab.seismo.ethz.ch/efehr/eshm20>.

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Appendix A:

This annex presents spatial maps of the \log_{10} yearly cumulative earthquake occurrence rates computed from the reference smoothed seismicity model (SSM) developed for ESHM20. The maps illustrate how seismicity rates vary across the model domain for different magnitude thresholds, providing visual insights into the expected seismic productivity in space and magnitude.

The maps are shown for magnitude thresholds of $M \geq 4.5$, 5.1, 6.1, and 7.1, illustrating the decay in cumulative seismicity with increasing magnitude. All maps are computed on a uniform grid of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ and show \log_{10} of the annual rate of exceedance per km^2 .

In regions with well-mapped active faults, the reference SSM acts solely as a background model, contributing off-fault and lower-magnitude activity. In these areas, large-magnitude rates are governed by the fault source models. In intraplate or low-seismicity zones, the reference SSM is used as an alternative to area sources, providing spatially continuous estimates of seismicity rates.

Figure A.1: Spatial distribution of yearly earthquake rates for $M \geq 4.5$ from the reference SSM. The rate field is computed using an adaptive power-law kernel with optimized parameters ($n = 49$, $\rho = 10$ km). The net yearly rate of events with $M \geq 4.5$ is approximately 112.6 events/year. The colour scale shows $\log_{10}[\text{Rate (km}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1})]$.

Figure A.2: Spatial distribution of yearly earthquake rates for $M \geq 5.1$ from the reference SSM. The rate field is computed using an adaptive power-law kernel with optimized parameters ($n = 49$, $\rho = 10$ km). The net yearly rate of events with $M \geq 5.1$ is approximately 29.61 events/year. The colour scale shows $\log_{10}[\text{Rate} (\text{km}^{-2}\cdot\text{year}^{-1})]$.

Figure A.3: Spatial distribution of yearly earthquake rates for $M \geq 6.1$ from the reference SSM. The rate field is computed using an adaptive power-law kernel with optimized parameters ($n = 49$, $\rho = 10$ km). The net yearly rate of events with $M \geq 6.1$ is approximately 3.25 events/year. The colour scale shows $\log_{10}[\text{Rate} (\text{km}^{-2}\cdot\text{year}^{-1})]$.

Figure A.4: Spatial distribution of yearly earthquake rates for $M \geq 7.1$ from the reference SSM. The rate field is computed using an adaptive power-law kernel with optimized parameters ($n = 49$, $\rho = 10$ km). The net yearly rate of events with $M \geq 7.1$ is approximately 3.25 events/year. The colour scale shows $\log_{10}[\text{Rate (km}^{-2}\text{-year}^{-1})]$.

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